

THE ESTABLISHMENT OF THE FIRST STATES IN THE TERRITORY OF UZBEKISTAN

Ramatov Murat

3rd year student of History faculty of Navoi State Pedagogical Institute
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ABSTRACT

Our country The first countries in Uzbekistan appear to be Ancient of states names and internal and external policy about to the students and to those interested data to give Each of the state development , own development and crisis effect did factors complete open to give In our area is located castles and their own period prospects look put

Uzbekistan the first of states payol to be years when it passed of Uzbekistan independent to be with starting with his evolution and development being came from processes is one This of Uzbekistan colonies , culture and strictly relations with depends although the document some parts , states and another series another entrepreneurship types and deficiencies too own into takes Uzbekistan long and complicated to history have being his borders centuries during a lot times moved Country in history the most important from events one in 1991 Soviet Union disintegrated , Central in Asia one how much new independent of states appear to be take came As a result Uzbekistan own in history the first times one how much new countries with borderline it has been . Geopolitical in dynamics this change Uzbekistan and his neighbors with relations and wider region for important influence showed .

Uzbekistan with next door countries between new boundaries installation and relationships designation process to difficulties full it has been . Areas , resources and of the population distribution , as well as in the region safety and stability in the matter of disagreements there is was However , this to difficulties despite , Central Asia countries sure boundaries set giving , each of the state right and obligations set giver agreements according to negotiations take to go succeeded it has been . Central in Asia boundaries designation to the process leadership did main from principles one peace to live and cooperation idea was Each state own neighbors with good relationships storage and common problems solution in doing act

together recognized its importance . This approach confidence to strengthen help gave and today's until the day continue doing cooperation the soul strengthened .

Uzbekistan , Middle Asia in the region ancient of states appear to be with depends . This is the process ancient East statehood history with organic depends . Bronze in the period artificial to water based on farming , Middle Asia of the farm basis organize reached Do not water of farming high fertile forms in society solution doer to changes take came Medium Asia peoples of his ancestors first statehood development ancient cities history with organic depends was Ancient East , Ancient close East that too called , modern close to the east approx suitable coming in the area first civilizations homeland has been area is considered This on the ground the following civilizations there is was :

1. Mesopotamia : Modern Iraq , Turkey southeast , southwest Iran and northeast Syria.
2. Ancient Misr : Of Egypt ancient period civilization .
3. Ancient Iran : Elam, Media , Parthia and Persia .
4. Anatolia and Small Asia and Armenian mountains : of Turkey Eastern Anatolia region , Armenia , northwest Iran , south Georgia and western Azerbaijan .
5. Levant : Modern Syria , Lebanon , Israel , Palestine and Jordan .
6. Cyprus and Arabia half island

Ancient close East history from AD in the previous 4th millennium of Sumer appear to be with starts . This is history finish the date is different is considered Ancient close East the world civilization from their cradles one is considered Here intensive village economy the first times done increased He is the first dense city population of points appear to be , social stratification , centralized the government and empires , organized religion and organized war such as many familiar civilization of institutions development take came It is also the first writing system , first alphabet (abjad), in history the first money unit and the law of codes creation , astronomy and mathematics basics put initial achievements and the wheel invention saw

Central in Asia boundaries designation process regional stability and safety is also important effect showed O'z borders sure designation and disputes solution reach mechanisms installation through Central Asia countries conflicts probability to reduce , mutually in relationships in advance according to accuracy and transparency to increase help gave This is in turn , economic development and cooperation for more stable and safe environment to create service did However , Central in Asia boundaries designation process own from problems case it's not was Region countries in the middle of borders sure location , border in the regions living ethnic and religious of minorities rights about concerns according to disagreement and disagreements surface came These issues solution to do for thorough negotiations and compromise to arrive need was , but in the end Central Asia countries all participants satisfying to agreements reach they took

Own borders designation and disputes solution to do mechanisms Create according to act together through region countries confidence to strengthen and today's in the day relationships in formation continue doing mutually respect the soul to develop succeeded it has been . of Uzbekistan geographical location do not bridge own into because it takes file appear to be his the most big resources between appearance occupies Today's in the day Uzbekistan Ferghana 4 countries in the valley acceptance to do one by one although the document independent to be provide state and work in release necessary changes to existence trust harvest to be need

Foreign countries with mutually relationships independent manage of Uzbekistan economic , political and cultural in his life important place to take over take will come . Uzbekistan own living between peoples influences and cooperation development for to this very attention to give need With that together , of Uzbekistan independence provide for necessary has been

merger to see necessary of Uzbekistan independent state with connections strengthening , connections and relationships to develop help will give . This is the process of Uzbekistan international in society own place to take over help will give and to him help to give living peoples o' opposition own into maybe cooperation and loyalty waits of Uzbekistan international culture , art the world countries with exchange possibility will give .

Of Uzbekistan social payment according to local and economic regimes , economic and culture systems mutually influences improve there is also necessary . That's why , payol otherwise , Uzbekistan again one step before there is no taken can Of this for , it is of the country economic , cultural , political and political in sections necessary it requires ten .

Uzbekistan the first of states payol to be very important process . In general Uzbekistan and to him next door of states borders designation process region in history important event it has been . This is Central Asia countries between cooperation and of cooperation new period starting from gave and economic development and regional integration for more stable and safe environment to create help gave

References

1. History back will not return collection . 2004
2. I. Karimov " Historical without memory the future no " . 1998 - year
3. I. Karimov " High spirituality invincible power " . 2008
4. Azamat Zie " Uzbek statehood history " 2000

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